

Synthetic load profile generation for production chains in energy intensive industrial subsectors via a bottom-up approach

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ABSTRACT

Iron & Steel, Pulp & Paper, Non-Metallic Minerals and Chemical & Petrochemical are the most energy intensive subsectors, even though they utilise only a limited range of production processes compared to other sectors like Machinery or Food & Beverages. To support future efforts for decarbonising the European industry, this study aims to develop a methodology to correctly and dynamically depict all relevant production processes of the mentioned subsectors and to generate synthetic load profiles (LP)¹ based upon their consumption and generation behaviour. In a first step, the energy intensive subsectors and their main production processes are identified. A standardised research approach is used to correctly depict their characteristics e.g. runtime, energy consumption and generation, unit sizes etc. Next, a methodology for modelling the timely behaviour of these production processes and for generating synthetic LPs is developed. This method is based upon the bottom-up approach of discrete-event simulation combined with stochastics. The developed methodology is then implemented into the simulation software *Ganymed*. Finally, the results of this methodology are validated via a case study, modelling the primary steel production route of an Austrian steel mill. In overall, the synthetic electricity LP shows good approximations to the measured one with a mean absolute percentage error of 6.08% for the simulated five days in total. However, a stronger deviation of the generated LP compared to the measured counterpart can be noted at the last two days. This deviation results from a reduction of the capacity during the real life production. This, however, can be taken into account in the synthetic generation given a more extensive data basis. Consequently, *Ganymed* can be deemed as a suitable software for generating energy consumption and generation behaviour of processes and production chains of energy intensive industries.

1. Introduction

The European industry accounts for 21% of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions (energy and process related) (European Commission, Statistical Office of the European Commission, 2021) and 20% of the gross inland energy consumption in 2020 (European Environment Agency, 2021). Thus, this sector undoubtedly has to take part in the energy transition. In addition, efforts to decarbonise the industry are even higher when compared to other sectors: This is due to its process diversity, technological complexity, varying GHG emission sources (e.g. process specific emissions) and use of energy carriers from different feedstock (Fleiter et al., 2018).

The development of comprehensive energy system models may help

to overcome these challenges and align the industrial sector with the European net-zero GHG emission goals (European Commission, 2019). The dynamic character of simulation models allows to get hold of fast changing trends and technologies, evaluate their impacts on the physical energy system efficiently and, therefore, support the strategic decision-making for the energy transition.

To integrate this sector into such models, technological and systemic characteristics of the industry have to be taken into account. This can be achieved by structuring the industrial sector throughout a standardised approach and applying suitable calculation methodologies. Due to increasing volatility of the energy system, models further examine future grid capacities and demands for energy suppliers (Böckl, 2020). Here, the calculation of timely resolved behaviour of energy consumption and generation of industrial consumers in terms of load profiles (LP) play a

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¹ LP ... Load Profile.

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List of acronyms			
LP	Load Profile	min	Minutes
GHG	Greenhouse Gas Emissions	h	Hour
PV	Photovoltaic	EAF	Electric Arc Furnace
kWh	Kilo Watt Hours	GUI	Graphical User Interface
MWh	Mega Watt Hours	CHP	Combined Heat & Power
TWh	Tera Watt Hours	SIP	Sintering Plant
e.g.	Exempli Gratia	COP	Coke Oven Plant
NACE	Nomenclature statistique des activités économiques dans la Communauté européenne	BF	Blast Furnace
IEA	International Energy Agency	DS	Desulphurisation Unit
PVC	Polyvinyl Chloride	BOF	Basic Oxygen Furnace
P	Power	LF	Ladle Furnace
t	Tonnes	VOD/VD	Vacuum (Oxygen) Degasser
		HR	Hot Rolling
		MAPE	Mean Absolute Percentage Error
		TV	Total Variability

key factor. The generation of such LPs will be discussed in detail in this paper.

1.1. State of research

In recent years, numerous studies and models on analysing the industrial energy system have been developed. Mostly, the main aim of these are to investigate long-term emission reduction, higher energy efficiencies and implementation of renewables or future technologies (Fais et al., 2016). The results of these studies are then integrated into model-based decarbonisation strategies for either the whole industrial sector (Fais et al., 2016), individual subsectors (Bajpai, 2016) or breakthrough technologies (e.g. by investigating the impact of these technologies like PV plants or electrolyser) (Rootzén, 2015). In most of them, the development of an emission or energy reduction pathway is statically calculated and determined.

In regard to timely resolved energy consumption, a range of studies and models on the dynamic characteristics of consumer structures of the energy system can be found in literature. Especially for the mobility and private sector, various models were developed:

In the mobility sector, models for simulating the energy consumption of electric vehicles at charging stations were developed to determine the effects on the power grid. These approaches are established either based on measured data or accurate modelling of the driver's behaviour (Iversen et al., 2014). The mentioned data origins from measurements at charging stations (Neaimeh et al., 2015) or from statistical data (Leou et al., 2014). Vopava et al. (2020) examined these approaches in detail.

In the residential and private sector, standard load profiles for electricity are calculated for groups of more than 400 single consumers under 100 MWh (e-Control AT). However, the accuracy of the standard load profiles strongly decreases with a decreasing number of single consumers due to the stronger variation of the cumulative loads. Pflugradt and Muntwyler (2017) developed a holistic model for simulating synthetic profiles of single residential consumers in low-voltage grids without utilising standard load profiles. The bottom-up calculations within this method include various parameters, e.g. behaviour of the residents, consumptions of household appliances etc. A similar methodology was developed by Müller et al. (2020). Esslinger and Witzmann (2012) created an energy demand model for generating LPs of smaller consumer groups, entirely based on probabilistic calculations. Both bottom-up approaches exhibit valid approximations to the behaviour of the selected consumer categories and groups.

However, only a small number of studies on generating load profiles of consumers in the industrial sector can be found in literature. Starke et al. (2013) examined synthetic LPs of various industrial subsectors via probabilistic, mixed bottom-up and top-down approaches. The study identifies energy intensive manufacturing processes and typical

production hours of various industrial subsectors to calculate a range of load factors adjusted to the individual sector. Via genetic algorithms a standardised LP is created. Based on the identified load factors, the standard LP is adapted according to the selected subsector in terms of fluctuating energy demand and overall consumption. The results of this approach are hourly-resolved electricity LPs, for which analysis of demand response possibilities for the chosen subsector are conducted.

Other studies simulate LPs for selected production plants (Dock and Kienberger, 2019) or industrial parks (Hernández et al., 2012) by e.g. analysing and clustering of measured data and identifying consumption patterns. Measures for optimising production processes or implementing new technologies at the plant site can be derived from these analyses. However, these approaches require a large scaled data basis.

Throughout this literature research it was found that a holistic framework for generating detailed, synthetic LPs for various energy carriers of all industrial subsectors has not been developed yet. However, for investigating the future energy system and requirements for grid operators and suppliers such models are crucial. Based on this knowledge, the comprehensive simulation software *Ganymed* (Binderbauer, 2021) was developed. The aim of this paper is to present the methodology and results of this tool.

1.2. Open research questions and structure of this paper

In context of the industrial sector, only a small amount of methodologies for the generation of synthetic LPs was found in literature, as concluded above. This leaves unanswered research questions and space for developing novel LP generation methods, which will be covered throughout this paper:

- Which approach shall be applied to develop a simulation methodology covering energy intensive, industrial subsectors? In what way shall industrial processes be standardised for integrating into the investigated methodology? Which simplifications have to be used? Which limitations and assumptions (e.g. system boundaries) have to be respected?
- How can individual process properties and conditions (e.g. batch/continuous operations, various material streams, parallel/serial process alignment, ...) be depicted accurately? How can deterministic and stochastic simulation methods be combined?

Within this paper, the development of the proposed and underlying methodology of the software *Ganymed* is presented, answering the questions above. After outlining the main results of an extensive literature research in Section 1.1, a comprehensive methodology description follows in Section 2. Therefore, the European industrial landscape is divided into subsectors by IEA (International Energy Agency, 2021) and

classified into groups regarding their energy consumption. (Section 2.1). The characteristics, typical production chains and processes of these subsectors were researched and are structured in Section 2.2. As a next step, a methodology based upon discrete-event simulation was developed and enhanced (Section 2.3). To prove the functionality of the developed methodology, Section 3 presents and discusses a selected case study of an existing production plant of the Iron & Steel sector in Austria.

2. Methods

2.1. Methodological research, approach and classification of the industrial landscape in Austria

To develop a comprehensive solution for generating LPs of various production chains of different industrial subsectors, an overall methodology approach was developed. This approach includes the following steps:

1. Division and classification of the industrial landscape
2. Research on characteristics of subsectors and processes
3. Development of a suitable methodology for generating synthetic LPs of researched industries
4. Integration of the developed methodology into the simulation software *Ganymed*

Industrial subsectors are defined by the International Energy Agency (IEA) (International Energy Agency, 2021) as depicted in Fig. 1. These sectors exhibit a good basis for further investigations. Additionally, other product specific classifications like NACE (Statistics Austria, 2008) were assessed. However, they were deemed as non-suitable for overall simulation approaches due to their higher level of complexity and sectioning.

Sejkora et al. (2020) assessed the primary energy consumption for all IEA subsectors in Austria with 139 TWh, as their shares are shown in Fig. 1. This study aims to depict the most energy intensive subsectors Iron & Steel, Pulp & Paper, Chemical & Petrochemical and Building Materials/Non-Metallic Minerals. Based on extensive literature research on these subsectors and their processes following key characteristics can be defined:

- Energy intensive subsectors are part of the primary production or industry and either extract and process raw or produce basic materials (European Economic, 2009).

- These subsectors exhibit a limited range of varying production processes and principles. Therefore, product variety is smaller than in other manufacturing subsectors, e.g. Machinery (Lechtenböhrer et al., 2016). The production processes can be described as homogenous.
- Only a few of the production processes account for the main share of energy consumption within a subsector (Johansson et al., 2012).

Due to these characteristics, production chains and their underlying processes can be depicted throughout a bottom-up approach. The generation of LPs of energy intensive subsectors are the main subject of this study.

2.2. Research on characteristics of industrial subsectors and processes

Fig. 2 depicts the method for researching various production chains and processes of the selected energy intensive subsectors.

Throughout an extensive literature research regarding the mentioned industries, typical production chains and their characteristics were identified. These characteristics were then studied and the most energy intensive and commonly operated processes within these production chains were further investigated. An overview of these selected production chains can be seen in Table 1. Certain product specific processes are operated in every subsector at the end of production in order to guarantee characteristics of the product to be produced (e.g. coating of high-quality paper).

In a next step, the scope of investigated production chains for further analyses was defined. Extraction, mining and transportation activities were excluded from the analyses as they are often located outside of the production/manufacturing plant border. Individual product refinement steps like coating of paper or special surface treatments of finished steel billets were not considered further as they exhibit lower energy demands compared to the main processes and are difficult to depict via a bottom-up analysis due to their variety and complexity. However, *Ganymed* enables user-defined process individualisation and system boundaries, which make an implementation of said processes possible, provided a sound data basis is given.

The identified processes were examined in more detail in a next step. Parallel and serial subproduction chains are implemented to meet the individual needs in different industrial plants. For example, regarding the Pulp & Paper sector, discontinuously working pulp digesters are operated in parallel and alternating to ensure a steady flow of pulp for the continuous follow-up processes (Paul Binderbauer, 2021). In the

Fig. 1. Share of primary energy consumption of industrial subsectors by IEA in Austria.

Fig. 2. Standardised approach for researching characteristics of industrial subsectors and processes.

Iron & Steel sector large process units like the electric arc furnace (EAF) are mostly implemented as a single process (Heinen, 1997). The follow-up processes are then operated in parallel and alternating to cope with the according batch sizes efficiently (Degner, 2009).

For generating synthetic, industrial LPs, detailed information on batch and continuous processes are essential. Fig. 3 shows the standardised approach, which defines the researched process characteristics. Continuous working equipment (e.g. paper calendar) is characterised by a steady throughput (e.g. material flow in t/h). Batch processes (e.g. EAF) are loaded with a certain quantity of material (e.g. in tonnes) and operate for individual durations (e.g. in hours, minutes, ...). Typical ranges of energy consumption or generation can be determined for both process operations. These energy related characteristics are assessed for the energy carriers Electricity and Direct Fuel as well as for the useful energy categories Steam and Thermal Heating (see Section 2.3).

Table 1

Main production chains of energy intensive subsectors, which were researched and analysed throughout this study.

Iron & Steel	Pulp & Paper	Non-Metallic Minerals	Chemical
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Blast Furnace Route (Corradini et al., 1999; Degner, 2009; Ecker, 2013; European Steel Association, 2007; Remus et al., 2013) • Electric Arc Furnace Route (Aichinger, 2015; Heinen, 1997; Messer Group) • (Product Specific Processes (e.g. Alloying, Design of Final Product (e.g. Rails, ...)) (Corradini et al., 1999; Degner, 2009)) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pulp Production via Kraft, Sulphite, Thermomechanical or Mechanical Processes (Bajpai, 2016; Chan and Kantamaneni, 2015; Jacobs Greenville and Institute of Paper Science and Technology, 2006; Rahnama Mobarakeh et al., 2021; Suhr et al., 2015) • Paper Production (Bajpai, 2016; Chan and Kantamaneni, 2015; Jacobs Greenville and Institute of Paper Science and Technology, 2006; Rahnama Mobarakeh et al., 2021; Suhr et al., 2015) • (Product Specific Processes (e.g. Coating, Sizing, ...)) (Bajpai, 2016)) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cement Production (Fleiter et al., 2013; Gruber) • Lime Production (Schimmel, 2019; Szednyj and Brandhuber, 2017) • Glass Production (Fleiter et al., 2013; Moser et al., 2017) • Brick and other Ceramic Production Routes (Fallmann and Weiß, 2018; Moser et al., 2017) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Oxygen Production (Brown et al. Messer Group; Shen and Wolsky, 1980) • Ammonia Production (Brown et al.; European Commission, 2007) • Chlorine Production (Brown et al.; Resource Dynamics Corporation, 2002) • Ethylene Production (Brown et al. Gaines and Shen) • Polyethylene Production (Brown et al.) • Polypropylene Production (Meyers) • (Further Processing Routes (e.g. Fertiliser, Urea, PVC, ...)) (Fleiter et al., 2013))

The results of this methodology heavily depend on the quality of the presented data in literature. It was found that mostly consumption and generation is issued in average, specific energy consumption. For example, a batch working pulp digester consumes electricity in a range from 44 to 170 kWh/t_{Air_Dried_Pulp} (Bajpai, 2016) and steam from 700 to 1370 kWh/t_{Air_Dried_Pulp} (Jacobs Greenville Institute of Paper Science and Technology, 2006). To calculate process specific LPs based on specific energy consumption, as described above, these values are multiplied by the process throughput for continuous and by capacity per operating time for batch processes. The resulting LPs can be described as an average load profile for this process (Fig. 3 (a)/(c)). However, in some cases, singular, process specific LPs were found in literature (see Section 3). These LPs are then implemented into the simulation framework (Fig. 3 (b)/(d)). Additionally, the user can modify the process' properties freely within *Ganymed*.

2.3. Methodology for the generation of synthetic load profiles

2.3.1. General methodology

Table 2 shows the target categories Electricity, Direct Fuel, Steam and Thermal Heating for which LPs can be generated. Direct Fuel refers to energy carriers, which transfer heat directly onto the product during energy conversion (e.g. oil, gas, coal, biomass, etc.). The distinction

Fig. 3. Description of Continuous and Batch Processes: (a) Resulting LP based upon specific energy consumption of continuous processes; (b) Predefined singular LP of continuous processes from literature or measurements; (c) Resulting box-like LP based upon specific energy consumption of batch processes; (d) Predefined singular LP of batch processes from literature or measurements.

Table 2
Target categories of the LP generation in reference to useful energy categories and application temperature ranges.

Energy Carriers/Useful Energy Categories (European Commission, Statistical Office of the European Commission, 2021)	Application & Temperature Range in <i>Ganymed</i>
Electricity	-
Direct Fuel	High-Temperature Range
Steam	Medium-Temperature Range
Thermal Heating	Low-Temperature Range

between Direct Fuel, Steam and Thermal Heating was made due to applied temperature ranges.

As mentioned above, energy intensive subsectors utilise a limited amount of processes, which can be depicted effectively throughout a bottom-up approach. For generating the desired LPs discrete-event simulation was found to be the most promising bottom-up methodology. This method was implemented via object-oriented programming in Python and further improved to adequately depict industrial processes, as described in the following sections.

Discrete-event simulation depicts a sequence of interactions of i active components (e.g. tonnes of steel) with m resources (e.g. industrial processes like blast furnace, etc.) via time-proceeding events as described by Banks (2003). This simulation principle was then embedded into the standalone application *Ganymed*.

Fig. 4 describes the adapted discrete-event environment in terms of generating LPs for industrial processes.

As depicted in Fig. 4, the environment needs to be set up (c) before initiating the simulation (d) through *Ganymed's* graphical user interface (GUI) (b). The user controls both actively by defining a production chain from an amount of individual processes as well as a number i of active components at first, which shall then be processed during the simulation.

During setup, the simulation environment (a) receives all needed information from outside its boundaries (e). This information contains a blueprint for a generic process class including default literature data (e.g. the process' name, its operating type (batch/continuous), unit size, capacity, throughput, energy consumption and generation, information on energy fluctuations, ...). Based on this blueprint n specific process resources (e.g. pulp digester containing default values) are created (f).

Based on the user's input, a certain amount m of processes of the same resource n involved in the production chain are created in the software interface (e.g. two blast furnaces operating in parallel). The derived m objects (g) inherit the default information of the corresponding class resource. However, their characteristics can be adapted via the software interface before initiating the simulation (h). This enables a dynamic process individualisation by the user on top of the included default data from literature.

The user then establishes the order in which the created processes are aligned by defining a coordination matrix (see Section 2.3.2.2). Furthermore, processes can run in serial or parallel. These simulation specific features are explained in the following sections. Through the system preferences, the user can specify a number i of active components as a main product, e.g. $i = 100$ tonnes of steel per total runtime. This

Fig. 4. Adaption of discrete-event simulation in Ganymed.

amount will then be passed through the user-defined process order sequentially.

Throughout the process order, resources are occupied by a number of active components sequentially according to their capacity. The corresponding events (i), which occur at different times over the simulation, halt the resource/process for the defined operating time, while active components not involved in the processing are aligned in a queue in front of this resource. During these process durations, singular LPs for the individual process steps are calculated. After the simulation has finished, the LPs of the object resources are summed up to represent the total LP of the defined production chain (j).

Fig. 5 shows a simplified generation of the overall LP based on summation of two individual process consumptions. In this example, two serial processes operate two active components (one tonne per component each) during the simulation ($i = 1, 2$). Both resources vary in regard to their runtime and consumption. The coloured rectangles in the depicted overall LP present the singular, average profiles of the corresponding processes. As the first tonne ($i = 1$) is processed in resource 1 over an operating time of 2.7 min, the associated singular LP is added into the chart. The second tonne ($i = 2$) waits in the queue of resource 1. After the processing is finished, the first tonne is passed onto the second resource, which creates the first blue share of the total LP at $t = 2.7$ min to 4.7 min. At the same time, the second active component ($i = 2$) is processed in resource 1. This component then occupies the second resource after the finished operation in process 1. Thus, a total LP (yellow line) of the electricity demand of this production chain can be

depicted.

2.3.2. Application for industrial processes

Due to the large amount of variations of industrial processes and their operation, the basic discrete-event simulation approach needs to be enhanced extensively. Certain features and topics, which ensure a valid approximation to real production chains, are included in the simulation software Ganymed. The underlying methodology is explained in the following sections.

2.3.2.1. Behaviour of batch and continuous processes. To realise batch and continuous operating types, the smallest functional unit of one tonne of the finished product is specified as active component, as described above. Therefore, the capacity attribute of continuous processes is set to 1. The operating time of these occupied processes for one tonne of the finished product is defined by the reciprocal of the throughput (t/h). Continuous processes don't contain idle times like charging or discharging activities. A constant flow of active components and/or long enough queues for every continuous working resource is required. Short timely offsets of arriving active components in long production chains in the simulation (resulting in idle times and fluctuating energy demand) are bridged. Thus, a continuous LP is calculated as described in Section 2.2.

The capacity of batch operating processes is defined by literature data or the user, e.g. 65 tonnes of steel. The resource is loaded with the active components over a certain period of time until the capacity is met.

Fig. 5. (a) Resulting LP of a simplified production route (resource 1 and resource 2); (b) Process flow diagram for resource 1 and resource 2 as well as their properties.

This duration, as part of the overall process' runtime, is defined as the charging phase and results in a null line in the corresponding LP (Fig. 3 (d)). The processing with its specific energy consumption starts as the event of the batch resource is halted for the defined operating time. After this time has elapsed, the active components are forwarded to the next process in the order of arrival for a defined discharging time. For the period of the operating time, a singular LP is calculated.

2.3.2.2. Alignment of processes. As described above, processes of production chains can be aligned freely by the user through the GUI of *Ganymed*. This also includes serial and parallel operating subchains. However, this requires boundaries, which define the start and end point for the flow of active components, as well as attributes, which depict the direction of the flow in between the processes.

For this purpose, a coordination matrix is applied, which contains all directional vectors including the individual addresses of the created resource objects. The overall production chain operates between a start and end object, defined by the user. Fig. 6 (b) shows a coordination matrix for the directional vectors of the depicted process chain (a). The first column in the coordination matrix contains the address of the object, where the active components are transferred from. The address in the second column describes the target object. At the beginning of the simulation, the algorithm searches the first column for the defined start object. On that basis, the following processes can be aligned and triggered sequentially according to the items in the coordination matrix.

As shown in Fig. 6 (a), processes can also be aligned in parallel by the user. In this case, the first column of the coordination matrix contains the address of the object, where the active components departure, multiple times (see (b) line 3 and 4). Therefore, the allocation of the components to the following processes has to be managed in a way, which depicts real operations sufficiently. Table 3 gives an overview of possible allocations for parallel processes, resulting from literature research (Máté Hegyháti and Ferenc Friedler, 2010). For example, the user can select individual objects, which are scheduled primarily (Object Preferences). Batch processes can be loaded consecutively considering the chosen degree or depending on their operating time.

2.3.2.3. Auxiliary material consumption and production. As the production of the main product progresses, various auxiliary materials are consumed and produced, e.g. production of black liquor in a pulp production plant (Rahnama Mobarakeh et al., 2021). These additional materials can affect the energy consumption and generation of the overall production plant.

As described in sections above, the main production route processes the main product. A total LP is generated through specific energy consumption assigned to tonnes of the main product, e.g. 100 kWh/t_{pulp}. Fig. 7 shows this main production line indicated by black, directional arrows.

The resulting coordination matrix for the main product is presented in Fig. 7 (b). Additionally, auxiliary material (green arrows) is processed in resource 3 and then added into resource 1. For this material stream, Fig. 7 (c) shows the associated extension to the coordination matrix. In this case, the process characteristics of resource 3, for example capacity,

Table 3

Implemented types for decision process of allocating product flows to follow-up parallel process subchains.

Allocation for All Process Types	Allocation for Batch Process Types Only
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Random Allocation • Consistent Allocation • Object Preferences 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Allocation based upon the degree of loading • Allocation based upon the operating time

energy consumption/generation, etc. are referenced to the actual auxiliary material, e.g. 200 kWh/t_{WoodChips}. To prevent inconsistencies in the overall material flow, mass conversion values are introduced to convert the auxiliary material to the main product. For example, the mass conversion ratio for wood chips to pulp in a Kraft production chain is about 2 (Rahnama Mobarakeh et al., 2021). For processes, which operate auxiliary material streams, the mass conversion is multiplied with the process' characteristics to reference to the main product:

$$200 \frac{kWh}{t_{WoodChips}} * \frac{2}{1} \frac{t_{WoodChips}}{t_{Pulp}} = 400 \frac{kWh}{t_{Pulp}} \quad (I)$$

At resource 1, the previously explained ratio can be taken into account. The methodology coordinates the chronological order in accordance to the implemented mixing and mass conversion ratios. Auxiliary material can also be produced as a by-product, e.g. black liquor (Fig. 7 (a) light-blue directional arrows). The resulting extension to the coordination matrix is shown in Fig. 7 (d). There, mixing and mass conversion ratios are also taken into account.

2.3.2.4. Implementation of stochastic methods. Singular LPs of stand-alone consumers can alternate over a vast range (Esslinger and Witzmann, 2012). Furthermore, the implemented data for selected processes, e.g. specific energy values like 100 kWh/t_{pulp} (see Fig. 3 (a)), depict only their average consumption and generation behaviour. To bypass certain insecurities and gaps in the data pool and in order to avoid box-like, unrealistic LPs, the bottom-up methodology is supported by stochastic methods, as suggested by Gao et al. (2018).

The first approach of implementing stochastic methods into the methodology is based on Gaussian distribution. This is already discussed in literature regarding LP generation for private households (Probst et al., 2011). Other references describe the application of Markov chains, e.g. for the simulation of big consumers like the EAF (Dock and Janz, 2020) or evaluation of lighting demand patterns in households (Widén et al.).

Fig. 8 (a) shows the application of Gaussian distribution. For a given standard deviation σ , a distribution for fluctuating the energy consumption or generation from μ can be calculated for every time step t of the load profile.

Both μ , and the standard deviation σ for selected process units are defined by literature data or the user. Based on this information, a cumulative distribution function $F(P)$ is calculated at t , as shown in Fig. 8 (a):

$$F(P) = \frac{1}{2} \left(1 + \operatorname{erf} \left(\frac{P - \mu}{\sqrt{2}\sigma} \right) \right) \quad (II)$$

Fig. 6. Alignment of processes in serial and parallel manner; (a) Showing a possible production chain along with its coordination matrix in (b).

Fig. 7. Production chain with auxiliary material routes; (a) Depicted production chain along with its coordination matrix (b) and its extensions in (c) and (d).

Fig. 8. Application of Gaussian distribution in LP generation of *Ganymed*: (a) Cumulative distribution function generating the deviation from μ at t ; (b) Resulting fluctuation of energy demand and charging/discharging phases of batch processes; (c) Resulting fluctuation of energy demand of continuous processes.

For the time step t , a random distribution factor z between 0 and 1 is drawn. This factor acts as a result of the cumulative distribution function $F(P)$. The associated power level P is calculated through cubic interpolation. The resulting fluctuations of energy consumption and generation is shown in Fig. 8 (b), for batch working processes, and Fig. 8 (c), for continuous processes, respectively.

Additionally, Gaussian distribution is also applied for alternating charging/discharging durations of batch processes (see Fig. 8 (b)).

2.3.2.5. Implementation of system boundaries. Calculations of energy flow balances can be performed for various system dimensions. For this, user-defined system boundaries were introduced into the methodology, which represent an essential calculation basis for LP generation of the defined production chain.

As energy flows intersect system boundaries, their timely behaviour can be assessed to generate LPs. To achieve this, these energy flows, representing the target categories in Table 2, were introduced into the

methodology, as depicted in Fig. 9 with bold arrows.

Object resources/processes can take part in the production itself and, therefore, consume final energy (e.g. electricity for wood debarker) or transform energy carriers within or outside the industrial plant (e.g. CHP-plant, blast furnaces, etc.), which are defined as “autoproducers” by the United Nations (United Nations, 2017).

As Fig. 9 shows, the integrated custom boundaries for generating LPs can be defined for system dimensions starting from single processes ((b) and (c)) to the overall plant (a). The resulting LPs are attributable to these different system levels. Fig. 9 (b) shows the defined boundary for a single production process, which consumes electricity only. The generated LP will only depict the consumption behaviour of this process. This also applies for the autoproducer in Fig. 9 (c). However, here, the resulting LPs of the produced categories steam and electricity will be negative. Because discrete-event simulation needs to handle specified mass flows, the mass flow of natural gas (depicted in light green directional arrows) has to be taken into account, while the energy input and

Fig. 9. Application of system boundaries in *Ganymed*; (a) Overall production plant boundary including (b) single production processes and (c) transformation processes.

output of this transformation process has to be defined accordingly via bold arrows. Fig. 9 (a) will only generate a LP for direct fuel as all other energy carriers are handled inside the boundary.

This range of user-defined system boundaries enables the generation of LPs for various system dimensions and included processes. For example, all final energy consuming processes can be depicted effectively. Through minor adaptations autoproducers within the plant border can be included in the calculation to generate LPs of the overall facility. Through this, not only the plant's consumption but also the generation of excess heat or electricity supply to the public energy system can be calculated respectively.

These key adaptations of discrete-event simulation represent the overall methodology of *Ganymed*.

3. Load profile validation case study

3.1. Overview

In the following section a selected case study is presented to validate the functionality of the developed simulation software *Ganymed* (Case study and software available at ganymed.ga) and its presented methodology. Therefore, the Blast Furnace route of Voestalpine GmbH in Donawitz in Austria is investigated. Vital information of the production chain design (Degner, 2009) and the processes' capacities (Ecker, 2013) originate from literature and open accessible platforms (e.g. Voestalpine Website). Consumption and generation behaviour of all unit operations are either based on measured singular LPs or averaged consumption characteristics. Ecker (2013) presents a measured electricity LP for the plant in Donawitz for a self-defined system boundary. The generated

Fig. 10. Overall production chain of selected case study.

Fig. 11. Implementation scheme of production chain in *Ganymed*.

synthetic LP will be compared to this measured profile in Section 3.3. Fig. 10 shows the overall production chain for producing steel billets in Donawitz from cradle to gate. Processes outside the shown system boundary defined by Ecker (2013) are not included in the LP generation. It is noted, that Fig. 10 doesn't present the quantity of process units involved, which are shown in Fig. 11. Since the presented LP only depicts electricity, the system boundary is set accordingly to intersect with the electricity consumption flows in Fig. 10. Process gases (e.g. Coke oven gas, blast furnace gas, converter gas, ...), natural gas and steam flows will not be respected within the simulation. The coke oven is excluded from the system boundary since coke is directly transported to the site in Donawitz. It is included in the overall production process nevertheless to depict a coherent Blast Furnace route. Additionally, the installed power plant in Donawitz is excluded from the calculation. However, *Ganymed* would be able to determine LPs for all energy categories as depicted in Fig. 10.

3.2. Model description

Based on the information above, a block flow chart (Fig. 11) for the implementation in *Ganymed* has been developed. The pig iron production in Donawitz is performed with one blast furnace (BF), which receives input materials (sintered iron ore and coke) from a sintering plant (SIP) and an external coke oven plant (COP, excluded from calculation). From literature data an average production output of raw steel of 180 t/h was determined. It is assumed, that the BF is operated continuously. The product batches for DS, BOF, LF and VD of 65 t result from the tapping process. This quantity is aligned with the continuous output of

180 t/h. It was found, that this ensures a steady flow of products within the defined production chain. The primary steel production includes two desulphurisation units (DS) and two basic oxygen furnaces (BOF) with a capacity of 65 t, which represents the size of one batch originated from the BF. This capacity is also assumed for the installed ladle furnaces (LD) and the vacuum (oxygen) degasser/decarboniser units (VD). The following operating units, continuous casting (CC) and hot rolling (HR), are operated continuously and are aligned with the production output of the BF.

Fig. 11 shows that the main batch processes are aligned in parallel. To ensure a steady flow of active components even through alternating processing times, the following processes can receive products from either two of the preceding units. This is realised through overlapping directional arrows in the coordination matrix. The two vacuum degasser units are installed to meet the required steel product specifications (Schröcker, 2014). Because these specifications can vary, both VD units are assumed to operate with a probability of 50%.

The main product route (black directional arrows) utilises “tonnes of steel” as active components. All corresponding processes characteristics are referred to these components. The system also includes the auxiliary material coal/coke, which is simulated as active component for the COP. The characteristics of COP are also referred to tonnes of steel. According to literature, the mass conversion factor is set to 1 (Degner, 2009).

Energy related consumption and generation of the processes involved were extracted from literature sources. All continuous processes are specified with averaged consumption values. The behaviour of batch operated processes, except the VD units, are characterised by predefined time series as of literature data (Fruehan, 1998). With regard

Fig. 12. Singular LP of the ladle furnaces from literature.

Fig. 13. Results of selected case study, comparing measured LP (Blue) to generated synthetic LP (Brown) for 5 working days. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

to this, Fig. 12 shows the singular LP for electricity of a ladle furnace unit as an example. The consumption behaviour results from different heating phases of the furnace for one ladle (65 t).

3.3. Results and discussion

The electricity LP of Ecker (2013) was measured within five working days (Monday – Friday). A synthetic LP for the production chain mentioned above with a depicted time of total 7200 min was generated respectively.

Fig. 13 presents the generated synthetic electricity LP in comparison to the measured profile by Ecker (2013) of the existing production site.

For the analysis and comparison of the synthetic LP to the measured profile, the average electricity consumption, total variability and the mean absolute percentage error (MAPE), following the depicted equation, were assessed:

$$MAPE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=1}^n \left| \frac{P_m - P_s}{P_m} \right| * 100\% \tag{III}$$

As $n = 7200$ represents the total number of data points/minutes, P_m constitutes the measured and P_s the electricity demand of the synthetic LP at the time t .

Table 4 presents the overall results and the deviation of the measured and synthetic LP. As the mean average percentage error of around 6.08% shows, the synthetic profile exhibits good approximations to the measured data in terms of average electricity consumption. The total

Table 4
Analysis and comparison of generated LP, covering the MAPE of mean electricity consumption and the TV of a representative day.

Mean Electricity Consumption	
Measured Load Profile:	24061.58 kW
Synthetic Load Profile:	25525.66 kW
MAPE:	6.08%
Total Variability (TV) of Day 2	
Measured Load Profile:	11023.21 kW
Synthetic Load Profile:	9571.21 kW
MAPE:	13.17%

variability per day (TV) presents the difference of maximum and minimum electricity demand for one day:

$$TV = \text{Maximum Electricity Demand} - \text{Minimum Electricity Demand} \tag{IV}$$

For the second day, the maximum variability of the measured LP is slightly higher than the synthetic profile, resulting in a mean average percentage error of 13.17%.

Fig. 14 shows the percentage error (PE) of all compared data points following the equation:

$$PE = \left| \frac{P_m - P_s}{P_m} \right| * 100\% \tag{V}$$

A strong deviation can be examined within the last two days. This is due to a noticeable fluctuation in the measured LP, resulting in a decreased electricity demand. Ecker (2013) reasoned this varied consumption in his work with an unexpected reduction of the production capacity and a partly shutdown of selected processes in Donawitz at that time. A polynomial fit (4th degree) shows the resulting fluctuation of the percentage error in Fig. 14. In this case, the fitted deviation rises to 30%. It is noted, that, under known circumstances regarding the alternating production capacity, a reduction of the percentage error within the last two days is possible.

Regarding the performance of Ganymed, the generation of the presented LP was completed in a runtime of 12.5 seconds. An examination of maximum queue lengths of active components for every process during this calculation shows lengths of 75 tonnes steel on average. This is in accordance to the chosen batch sizes (65 t) of batch operated processes (e.g. DS, BOF, LF, VD). The synthetic production chain exhibits no major idle times for the active components. Thus, the performance of Ganymed can be described as satisfactory. The performance will decrease when implementing further processes to the overall chain or by increasing the number of active components and runtime.

The mentioned altering production capacity or more detailed singular LPs of all involved process can heavily reduce the remaining percentage error. This requires a sound basis of information and data. However, the dynamic and adaptable characteristics of Ganymed allows the simulation of synthetic industrial LPs based on the user's data on top of the underlying default data. Missing or undetailed information could

Fig. 14. Percentage error and polynomial fit of all compared data points between measured and generated LP.

be improved by reinforced implementation of stochastic methods.

4. Conclusions & outlook

Throughout this paper, a comprehensive methodology for generating synthetic load profiles (LP) for the industrial landscape is presented. This approach involves energy intensive subsectors, which are characterised by homogenous process chains. It was found, that because of the limited amount of process and product variety of these raw material processing subsectors, the bottom-up methodology of discrete-event simulation is a suitable method for generating LPs for various energy carriers. This method was combined with basic stochastic models and improved to meet the depiction of industrial processes. A following case study modelling an existing Iron & Steel production chain proved the functionality of the established software.

In conclusion, the results of the presented methodology exhibit satisfactory approximations in depicting existing production chains and their timely resolved consumption. Thus, *Ganymed*, as discrete-event simulation is applied, adjusted to industrial processes and principles, can be deemed as a suitable software for generating synthetic load profiles of production chains of the selected subsectors. This approach requires a sound basis of information, which was created throughout this study and will be extended continuously. Furthermore, the methodology shall be improved further throughout future research. The presented case study shows the need for implementing variable production capacities. This can be achieved, for example, by introducing shift models or daytime-depending capacities into *Ganymed*. Shift models can, for example, incorporate non-producing times like weekends into the generated LPs. If this detailed information is not available, stochastic methods can be improved further by e.g. fluctuating the operating times or batch sizes of involved processes. For example, in the

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.130024>.

Appendix

The GUI of *Ganymed* was developed via the Python library “Tkinter”. A screenshot of the software interface is shown in Fig. 15. The process canvas enables the creation of various process objects and their user-defined arrangement via drag and drop. This ensures the specification of dynamic and flexible production chains during user setup. The alignment of processes is consistent with the mentioned methodology explained above.

Iron & Steel industry batches are often subject to alternating sizes. These alternating factors can be addressed via stochastics.

As described in Section 2.2, further processing steps like rail rolling mills or coating processes were not taken into account yet. This is due to the vast variety of possible processes involved, which is a disadvantageous factor for developing bottom-up simulation approaches. However, the development of a top-down simulation of other industrial subsectors can take these further processing steps into account. The implementation of this simulation approach will be the main topic of a follow-up study.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

Paul Josef Binderbauer: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Writing – original draft, Visualization. **Thomas Kienberger:** Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Thomas Staubmann:** Methodology, Validation, Data curation.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Fig. 15. Ganymed GUI Process Canvas and Preference Window of selected process.

The visual representation of a process object contains its consecutive number, a type symbol (batch/continuous), a process properties button, which opens the preference window (see Fig. 15), and four anchor points. The anchor points are the basis for incoming and outgoing material and energy flow arrows. The preference window displays the properties of the selected process object. These properties are the key information for the simulation framework and can be adapted by the user.

As mentioned above, the production chain operates within the defined start and end objects. After the user finished the arrangement of the overall production line, including start and end objects, the simulation can be initiated. A loading bar indicates the simulation’s progress.

After completion of the simulation, the user can switch to the calculation and results sheet as shown in Fig. 16. Here, the overall simulated load profile is displayed. This load profile includes the user defined simulation time as well as start-up and shutdown operations of the entire production chain. Via “Data Handling” the user can manipulate the simulated load profile, e.g. copy and paste representative parts of the load profile or cut statistical outliers or faulty boundary effects. Based on this, the user can generate and export a defined weekly load profile for the specific target values and energy carriers.

Fig. 16. Ganymed GUI Calculation & Results Sheet.

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